

Comparison of Self-Efficacy Beliefs of Urdu and English Teachers on The Basis of School Level

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Abstract

The Punjab government decision for changing medium of teaching from Urdu to English created disturbance among the teachers. Because Urdu was being used as medium of instruction even prior to creation of Pakistan, so, it was difficult for teachers to modify their minds, for English as language of instruction. Teachers showed less confidence in their capabilities and faced problems in adjusting themselves in new environment and while delivering education to the students efficiently. They were hesitant to absorb the change. Keeping in view the situation, the present study was conducted to measure and compare the willingness, confidence level and self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers of Urdu and English, on the basis of school level. The study aimed to explore the self-efficacy beliefs of school teachers and make a comparison on the basis of school level. For the purpose, the sample of teachers who were teaching Urdu or English to any of the classes from 1-10 was taken. Survey method was used and for multistage stratified random and convenient sampling technique was adopted. Sample size was 864 with 432 male teachers and 432 female teachers from 216 randomly selected schools, out of which there were 429 Urban and 435 rural teachers, 452 were teaching English and 412 were teaching Urdu in selected primary, elementary and secondary schools of the nine districts, selected from three administrative divisions of the Punjab province randomly.

Data were collected using adopted version of Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES) developed by Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk (2001)

For data collection the scale having 24 items on the three different sub scales was used. Bilingual version of the questionnaire was used for the convenience of respondents and analyzed using independent sample t-test, two way and multivariate analysis of variance. The study revealed that level of teachers' school showed valuable effects on the self-efficacy score of the teachers. Urdu teachers had more self-efficacious value; hence, Urdu teachers felt high level of contentment and comfort in teaching as compared to their colleagues i.e. English teachers. Moreover, primary school teachers demonstrated high level of self-efficacious power as compared to elementary and secondary school teachers.

Introduction

In societies, where several languages are spoken, discussion on medium of education is common. Generally public is in favor of mother language as medium of education. While, globalization is demanding a common language like English, among the nations for better coordination. Moreover, English is the widely used language in the field of science and technology, international business matters and communication. (Nunan 2003). In the multifaceted nations such as Pakistan where, Urdu is considered to be the national language, the School Education Department of Punjab declared 588 schools in phase I and 1764 in phase II as English medium Under the Education Sector Reforms of the Government of the Punjab. It was decided that from 1st April 2009, science and mathematics subjects will be taught in English. Moreover, it was decided that math and science subjects from class 6th in the selected public sector high schools of the Punjab will be taught in English language. (Directorate for Staff Development 2010).

This system was also being introduced in kindergarten classes of the other schools with as well. Similarly, social studies was to be taught in English language, in the schools having facility of English teachers. Progressively, these schools were to be shifted from Urdu medium to English medium by ensuring that subjects like Urdu, Islamic studies, Arabic and other optional subjects are taught in national language. It was also

decided that all public sector schools of highly populated cities having high literacy rate like Lahore, Sialkot, Faisalabad, Sargodha and Multan will use English as medium of instruction. Moreover, school Education Department of the Punjab planned to shift all the government institutions in the Punjab province from Urdu medium to English medium by the next few years (Directorate of Staff Development 2010).

This instant shift of teaching language from Urdu to English had several problems like teacher's abilities, motivation, incentives, knowledge about subjects and school environment itself. Similarly, student's behavior toward English as medium of study. Moreover, when medium of study is in foreign language, the quality of education depends upon the teacher's expertise and proficiency over that foreign language (Jones 2001), because, teachers acts as demonstrators both academically and socially as linguistic practitioners for the learners. Franklin (2000), argued that foreign language as a medium of instruction usually creates problem. On the other hand, if teacher's language is the same as subject's language, then teacher can effectively and easily teach the students and manage the class efficiently.

These hitches become more complicated for the teachers of public schools, which have students from diverse background, like socio-demographic and varying abilities in using English in different subjects (Ovando & Collier 2005). This situation demands for teachers to work against their proficient language and exhibit educational performance. Such difficult job generates unease among the teachers, which lead to disruptive personality, mental tension and stop teacher's capabilities, and in turn hampers student's academic achievements. So this anxiety creating factor is to dealt for better performance of the teachers (The Ohio State University, 2002). A number of teachers who are pathetic in English may suffer more than those teachers, who have command on this language, so this can affect the efficiency of weak teachers. Great sense of efficacy is one of the best recognized attribute of effective teachers (Henson, Kogan, & Vacha- Haase, 2001).

The self-viability convictions among the educators make motivation, enthusiasm, achievements, and interest (Bandura 2007). People with high motivational power exhibit anticipated outcomes with higher performance and have grater courage to persist difficulties. In contrast, weak motivation among peoples creates hardship and hopelessness. Berman et al. (2007) argued that self-efficacy beliefs among teachers play a dynamic role in determining the projects effectiveness, which are work to change their effectiveness.

The present study was designed to determine that, by settling these anxieties whether or not modification in medium of teaching is fruitful. The researcher envisioned to compare the self-efficacy beliefs among the teachers of class 1-10, by means of medium of teaching and to examine, whether the English teachers feel more proficient than the Urdu teacher.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to;

1. Compare Urdu and English teacher's self- efficacy beliefs.
2. Compare Urdu and English teacher's self- efficacy beliefs on the basis of school level (primary, elementary, secondary).

Research Questions

The study was to answer these research questions:

1. Are Urdu and English school teachers different on their mean self- efficacy scores?
2. Is there any difference between Urdu and English school teachers' mean self-efficacy scores on the basis of school level i.e. Primary, elementary, and Secondary?

Delimitations

Due to time and financial constrains the study was delimited to:

- I. Lahore Gujranwala and Faisalabad division only.
- II. Public sector schools of above mentioned divisions.

Research Design

This study was descriptive survey type in nature. The quantitative approach was used to analyze the data .

Population of the Study

Keeping in mind the objectives of present study, all the teachers of Urdu and English, irrespective of their designation from class 1-10 of all the public sector schools, primary, elementary and secondary level falling within the jurisdiction of the Punjab province was the target population of the study. Only two subjects - Urdu and English teachers teaching from class one to class ten in nine randomly selected districts from three administrative divisions of the Punjab, comprised the accessible population of the study.

Sample of the Study

Multistage stratified random sampling technique was used to draw sample from the population of school teachers from all public-sector primary, elementary, and secondary schools of the Punjab province.

Process for sample selection consisted of following steps.

1. The Punjab province has been divided into nine administrative divisions. These divisions are Lahore, Gujranwala, Faisalabad, Rawalpindi, Sargodha, Dera Ghazi Khan Sahiwal, Multan and Bahawalpur.
2. Three divisions from the nine administrative divisions (Lahore, Gujranwala and Faisalabad.) were selected randomly .
3. Three districts from each division were selected on convenience base.
4. The selected districts were Lahore, Sheikhpura, Kasur. Gujranwala, Sialkot, Gujarat. Faisalabad, Chiniot, Jhang.
5. All public sector schools from each district were distributed into three strata that are primary, elementary and secondary schools. Further each stratum was divided into two sub-strata on locale basis i.e. urban schools and rural schools and each sub-stratum was split into boys and girls schools. 04 Teachers form each school were selected two were Urdu Teachers and two were English teachers.

Total number of schools was 216

Total number of teachers was 864

Instrument of the Study

To measure the level of self-efficacy beliefs, among the target population, Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES) was adopted. This tool was established by Tschannen -Moran & Woolfolk (2001). TSES comprises 24 objects which are weighed on a 9 -points range with anchors at 1,3,5,7 and 9 respectively.

Pilot Testing of the Research Instrument

The purpose of pilot testing of research tool was to check the reliability, validity and the practical application of the research instrument and refine the items. Long form TSES (24 items) was translated into Urdu language to meet the objective of research. Views of the authorities were pursued to judge the validity of TSES for two languages i.e. Urdu and English. Specialists were invited to analyze the bilingual tool to check its face and

content validity. They were requested to judge the appropriateness and hitches regarding the native conditions. These experts also reviewed whether interrogative material in both languages communicates the same meanings for the respondents. After including recommendations of professionals, the TSES was pilot tested. The questionnaire was distributed among 20 respondents (10 males and 10 female) who are not included in the sample. Cronbach’s Alpha (α) was used to estimate the reliability of each item of the questionnaires and then estimate the overall reliability of questionnaire which come upto 0.96.

Analysis of Data

Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 21 was used for data analysis. Following procedure was used for interpreting the data.

- T-test was applied to measure the mean value of self-efficacy score of Urdu and English school teachers.
- Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was used to find out the change in mean values on the three sub scales of Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES).
- Two Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to measure the dissimilarity the mean self-efficacy values of Urdu and English teachers of secondary schools on the basis of gender, area, school level, teacher designation, and tenure of service.

Table . Evaluation of Self-efficacy beliefs between Urdu and English teachers

Medium of instruction	N	Mean	St. deviation	Mean difference	t-value	p-value
Urdu Teacher	412	142.73	28.955	15.87	11.618	0.000*
English Teacher	452	126.86	28.250			

*p<0.05

Table shows, mean score, standard deviation and mean difference score. The table indicates mean difference score with High value of self-efficacy among the Urdu teachers as compared to English teachers.

Table Indicating the Uni-variate Analysis of Variance for the differences between Urdu and English teacher on three sub scales of Teachers’ Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES)

Scales	Medium teaching in Schools	N	Mean Score	S.D	Mean Difference (UT-ET)	F- Value	Significance
Efficacy in Student Engagement	Urdu teacher	412	46.67	9.81	5.02	122.09	0.000*
	English teacher	452	41.54	9.66			
Efficacy in teaching Strategies	Urdu teacher	412	48.27	10.00	5.42	118.56	0.000*
	English teacher	452	42.85	10.83			
Efficacy in classroom management	Urdu teacher	412	47.79	10.31	5.41	127.08	0.000*
	English teacher	452	42.48	9.46			

*p<0.05

The F-value in every sub-scale of TSES regarding medium of teaching variances are stated in table 4.4. These values relate to medium of teaching which indicate that each sub-scales of TSES viz. Efficacy in students Engagement (F=122.09, p=0.000<0.01), Efficacy in teaching strategies (F=118.56, p=0.000<0.01), and

Efficacy in classroom management ($F=127.08$, $p=0.000<0.01$) varies meaningfully in Urdu and English teachers' self- efficacy beliefs. Urdu teachers' Efficacy in students Engagement ($M=46.67$, $S.D. =9.81$), and Efficacy in classroom management ($M=47.79$, $S.D. =10.31$) is greater as compared to English teachers whereas Efficacy in teaching Strategies ($M=48.27$, $S.D. =10.00$) is lesser then English teacher.

Table: Descriptive statistic of Urdu and English teachers on gender basis

		N	Mean	SD
Male	English Teacher	211	126.92	27.94
	Urdu Teacher	221	145.18	27.58
Female	English Teacher	241	126.81	28.56
	Urdu Teacher	191	139.99	30.22

Above table shows that total number of male English teachers is 211 and that total number of male Urdu teachers is 221 on the other hand total numbers of female English teachers is 241 and that total number of female Urdu teachers is 191.

Table Descriptive statistics of Urdu and English teacher on school level basis

		N	Mean	Mean Difference UT- ET	SD
Primary	English Teacher	97	124.41	32.21	25.879
	Urdu Teacher	72	156.62		26.733
Elementary	English Teacher	163	125.04	16.32	24.731
	Urdu Teacher	160	141.36		27.835
Secondary	English Teacher	190	129.79	8.28	31.900
	Urdu Teacher	182	138.07		29.082

Above table shows that total number of primary school English teachers is 97 S.D is 25.879 and that total number of primary school Urdu teachers is 72 S.D is 26.733 mean difference of Urdu teacher and English teachers is 32.21 on the other hand total number of elementary school English teachers is 163 S.D is 24.731 and that total number of elementary school Urdu teachers is 160 S.D is 27.835 mean difference of Urdu teacher and English teachers is 16.32 and total number of secondary school English teachers is 190 S.D is 31.900 and that total number of secondary Urdu teachers is 182 S.D is 29.082 mean difference of Urdu teacher and English teachers is 8.28.

Table: ANOVA table for Medium of Instruction and School Level for self-efficacy beliefs of teachers

Sources	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Significance
School Level	13849.20	2	6924.710	8.720	.000*
Medium of Instruction	142017.681	1	142017.681	178.839	.000*
School Level * Medium of Instruction	34664.790	2	17332.395	21.826	.000*
Error	1393662.862	1755	794.110		

*p<0.05

The self-efficacy of the school teachers was calculated by using two-way ANOVA on the basis of their medium of teaching and level of school. The results of two-way ANOVA test stated substantially noteworthy outcomes for school level, $F(2, 1755) = 8.72$, $p < .05$, demonstrating greater level of self-efficacy for primary school teachers (Table 4.10). Similarly, substantially remarkable outcomes for the medium of teaching, $F(1, 1755) = 178.83$, $p < .05$, demonstrating that Urdu teacher secured better self-efficacy. As the interaction amid school level and medium of teaching was also substantial, $F(2, 1755) = 21.82$, $p < .05$, a post hoc analysis with Tukey's HSD was done. The outcomes of post hoc got a link with descriptive analysis and exposed that teachers of primary level schools who have teach in Urdu showed higher level of self-efficacy as compared to teachers of elementary or Secondary schools regardless of their medium of teaching. Similarly, they secured higher level of self-efficacy as compared to teachers of primary schools, who use English as medium of instruction.

Table: Tukey HSD Comparison for Teachers' Self Efficacy

(I) School level of respondent	(J) School level of Respondent	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Secondary	Elementary	0.7	1.514	0.888	-2.85	4.25
	Primary	-4.07	1.795	0.061	-4.25	2.85
Elementary	Secondary	-0.7	1.514	0.888	-8.28	0.14
	Primary	-4.77*	1.84	0.026	-9.08	-0.45
Primary	Secondary	4.07	1.795	0.061	-0.14	8.28
	Elementary	4.77*	1.84	0.026	0.45	9.08

* p < 0.05

Above table shows 95% Confidence Interval at secondary school level of respondent at elementary level lower bound is -2.85, upper bound is 4.25 and primary level lower bound is -4.25, upper bound is 2.85.while 95% Confidence Interval at Elementary school level of respondent at Secondary level lower bound is -8.28, upper bound is 0.14and primary level lower bound is -4.25, upper bound is 2.85

Findings

As per outcomes of the data analysis the key findings of this study were;

1. Apparent variance was observed between the mean self-efficacy scores of Urdu teachers and English teachers. Substantial difference of the mean self-efficacy score indicated that Urdu teachers ($M= 142.73$, $SD=28.955$) were more Self-Efficacious as compared to English teachers ($M= 126.86$, $SD=28.250$); $t= 11.618$, $p= 0.05$.
2. Variance investigation indicated that school level has expressive effects, $F(2, 1755) = 8.72$, $p < .05$. Which means that primary school teachers have greater value of self-efficacy. The key impacts of medium of teaching were also substantial, $F(1, 1755) = 178.83$, $p < .0$, which represent that Urdu teachers secured greater level of self-efficacy (table 4.10). Interaction amid of school level and medium of teaching were observed meaningful, $F(2, 1755) = 21.82$, $p < .05$, when more exploration was carried out. The collective outcomes of the descriptive analysis represented that teachers doing jobs in primary schools and using Urdu teachers expressed High level of self-efficacy as compared to the teachers of elementary or Secondary school level, regardless of their medium of teaching. They secured greater value of self-efficacy level in comparison to teachers of primary school English teachers.

Conclusions

The conclusion were made after reviewing the outcomes of the study and detailed discussion of the findings of the research work as follows:

1. Urdu teachers had High level of self-efficacy in comparison with the English teachers. Which indicates that Urdu teachers recognize themselves more proficient and comfortable in carrying out of their responsibilities of teaching as compared to the English teachers.
2. The level of teachers' school showed valuable effect on the self-efficacy score of the teachers. Primary school teachers demonstrated High level of self-efficacious power as compared to elementary and secondary school teachers. Moreover, Urdu teachers had more self-efficacious value; hence, Urdu teachers felt high level of contentment and comfort in teaching as compared to their colleagues i.e. English teachers.

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